

The Coupling Constant Series and the Magical Weak Interaction

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June 7, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the weak interaction term of the new coupling constant, an interesting variation of the term can be made. An additional symmetry between the majestic (3) and the net variation, N_V , can be created. Such a variation of the term could lead to additional testable prediction regarding the nature of the weak interaction. Such a maneuver cannot be performed on any another element in the series. Reader is assumed to be familiar with the 8T thesis, as little will be elaborated on the equations presented in the paper.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Each term can be represented in the following way - using the prime critical line:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

In the 8T thesis, we have proven that the majestic (3), in the case of the electric coupling is the electron. The destabilizing factor yielding a net variation. Overall, the thesis main example was the third element in the series. therefore the weak interaction did not get enough interaction regrading a very interesting feature it posses.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \quad (3)$$

We can replace the net variation by the majestic (3) and the correctness of the term will retain. It could explain why the weak interaction is different in terms of its spin, and also allow us to make prediction regarding a fermion, which is analogous to the electron, which can get propagated by the boson of the weak interaction, , $N_V = +(3)$. The overall value is the same, there is a "symmetry" in such a variation, which is not attainable in any term of the coupling constant series. it could mean that the majestic (3) regarding the weak and the boson which is propagated are isomorphic to each other.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow [(8 * (3)) + 3] + (3) \quad (3.1)$$

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} (3) + N_V \right) + (3) \quad (3.2)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)